

Speech And Non-Speech Actions Corrective Work On Forming Self-Control Of Tempo-Rhythm

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Abstract: *The article discusses the issue of psychological and pedagogical support and assistance to children with stuttering, one of the most severe speech defects. The recommended exercises for eliminating stuttering consist in mastering and developing a rhythmic pattern, mastering the ratio of the duration of rhythmic work and pauses.*

Keywords — severe speech disorders (ONB), stuttering, formation of the ability to distinguish and observe pauses, rhythmic exercises.

INTRODUCTION.

The universal nature of tempo-rhythmic ability is manifested when a child learns visual, musical, speech activities. The development of the sense of tempo-rhythm occurs with the help of vision, hearing and movement coordination, and the use of the compensatory capabilities of the whole organism has a beneficial effect on speech and the rhythm of the body as a whole.

Taking into account that the speech therapy methods work with stuttering necessarily includes the control of the tempo-rhythm of speech, we have developed special methods that contribute to the gradual development of self-control of the tempo-rhythm of speech and non-speech movements. Correctional work consists of 4 stages.

In the first and second stages, children are taught the ability to perceive and evaluate the tempo of musical pieces, movements, etc., because a conscious assessment of tempo is a necessary condition for the development of self-control skills.

The third stage of work is aimed at teaching to control one's tempo in speech and non-speech actions.

In the fourth stage, children are taught to evaluate the tempo and rhythm of their own speech, which is of great importance for the development of self-control skills.

Each stage of correctional work has several sections. The time of each stage of the work is determined by the speech therapist separately for each group of children with different clinical forms of stuttering and depends on the individual characteristics of the structure of each child's disability.

The first phase is the preparation phase, which covers the first weeks of training, includes creating a speech routine, and includes the following sections.

1. To teach the ability to perceive and evaluate the tempo of actions. Instruction: "Imagine 3 boys. One is walking slowly, with difficulty, the second is walking at a normal pace, and the third is running fast, as if in a hurry. They all walk at

different tempos. See how this can be depicted in action. A speech therapist shows 3 children who show different tempos offers.

2. Animals also move at different tempos: the turtle walks very slowly, the cat is calm, average, the mouse runs fast. They all walk at a different tempo". 2. Drawing tempo-rhythms with the help of a visual example of a speech therapist - Instruction: "See how different tempo-rhythms can be depicted in pictures."

To teach the ability to perceive and evaluate the tempo of musical pieces. Music will be recorded. After each listening piece, a speech therapist will give an explanation. The music plays at a slow tempo. Note: "You should move very slowly to this melody, do slow dance moves, clap your hands very slowly, tap your feet very slowly."

The second stage. To teach the ability to perceive and evaluate the tempo-rhythms of adults and children around. Teaching to assess the tempo-rhythm of adult speech.

A speech therapist will demonstrate a poetic text of different speech tempos. Instruction: "Listen to a poem that can be read at different tempos. I will read at a fast tempo first."

The speech therapist commented: "I read it so fast that I couldn't understand anything." Now I read at a very slow pace. The speech therapist commented: "I read very slowly. It was difficult to listen to me." Now I study calmly and at a normal pace. Comment: "I read it calmly, smoothly, expressively, it was easy and pleasant to listen to."

2. Demonstration of different tempo-rhythms of speech in prose texts by a speech therapist. Instruction: "Hear how to read one story."

The third stage. Teaching to control the tempo-rhythm of one's speech.

It is conducted with small groups of children according to the clinical forms of stuttering. A metronome, excerpts from works, and demonstrative examples of tempo-rhythms are used.

Neurotic-like form of stuttering. 1. Synchronized pronunciation 1.1. Synchronized movements with hands (clapping). Synchronized movements with legs (stepping in place) and synchronized pronunciation of short poetic phrases, two lines. The speech therapist offers the game "Happy Journey". Instruction: "Now we are going on an interesting journey with you. We will ride a turtle that does everything slowly, and we will do everything at a slow tempo: we will move (clap / walk in place) and talk."

3. Simultaneous hand movements and emphasized poetic expressions in speech. I. Implementation of simultaneous foot movements and emphasized poetic phrases in speech. K. Drawing demonstrative samples of Tempo-rhythm (raindrops). Draw visual examples of two-line tempo rhythm (raindrops). Work with complaints is carried out in the same sequence

The fourth stage. Teaching to assess the tempo-rhythm of one's own speech

At this stage of the work, it is recommended to use a tape recorder, which helps to objectively assess the tempo and rhythm of one's speech, activate attention, and learn the skills of correct speech in a complex environment.

1. Learning to evaluate the tempo-rhythm of one's speech in a poetic text. The speech therapist suggests reciting any poem and evaluating its tempo. Then, the speech therapist offers the child to record the poem on a tape recorder and once again evaluate its tempo and rhythm, the expressiveness, loudness, and rhythm of the speech can also be noted. A speech therapist can help with both poem selection and pacing. After that, you can be invited to choose your own tempo / or a visual sample of a piece of music.

2. Teaching to evaluate the tempo-rhythm of one's speech in a prose text. The speech therapist suggests narrating the text or any other text that was mentioned in the training to assess his tempo. In order to more objectively evaluate the tempo-rhythm of his speech, the speech therapist offers to record the story on a tape recorder and evaluate the tempo-rhythm once again. After that, you can be invited to choose your own tempo or sample of a piece of music.

References

- [1] Belyakova L.I. Osnovnye logopedicheskie tehnologii, formation plavnoy rechi u zaikayushchihsya // Defektologiya. - 2001. - #4. - p. 49-53.
- [2] Bogomolova A.I. Ustranenie zaikaniya u detey i podrostkov. Iz opyta raboty: [Electronic resource] / A.I. Bogomolova // www.pedlib
- [3] Borisova EA. Sovmestnaya rabota vospitatelya i speech therapist po odoleniyu zaikaniya i ONR u detey senior gruppy.
- [4] Volkova GA. Logopedicheskaya rhythemics. - M.: Vldos. - 2002. - 272 p.
- [5] Voroshilova E.L. Sistema raboty s zaikayushchimisy doshkolnikami // Vospitanie i obuchenie detey s narusheniyami razvitiya. -2006. - #2. - p. 30.
- [6] Hegel NA. Roditelyam o zaikaniy detey i podrostkov // Defectology. - 1998. - No. 4. - p. 88-93.
- [7] Abidova, N. (2022). Problems of Preparing Future Defectologists to Work in the Conditions of Inclusive

Education. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 2505-2511.

- [8] Abidova, N. (2021). Organization Of The Work Of The Logo Teacher With Children With Disabilities In The Conditions Of Inclusive Preschool Practice. Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, 33382-33398.
- [9] Abidova, N. Z. (2013). Peculiarities of the Formation and Development of Vocabulary in Children with Vision Disorders. European Researcher, (2-3), 475-479.
- [10] Nilufar Abidova. (2021). Inclusive Education Of Children With Special Educational Needs. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 3(03), 476-480. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajssei/Volume03Issue03-74>